

Water Resources Research

Supporting Information for

Impact of Mineral Spatial Distribution on CO₂

Dissolution Rates in Multimineral Carbonate Rocks

Olatunbosun A. Adedipe, Yousef Al-Khulaifi, Sajjad Foroughi,

Qingyang Lin, Martin J. Blunt, Branko Bijeljic

Earth Science and Engineering Department, Imperial College London

Royal School of Mines, Prince Consort Rd, South Kensington, London SW7 2BP

Contents of this file

Text S1 to S2

Figure S1

Tables S1 to S8

Introduction

This supporting information document presents the results of a sensitivity analysis designed to quantify the impact of segmentation on calculated effective reaction rates, porosity, and permeability.

Text S1.

To evaluate the sensitivity of these calculated values to threshold variation, three grayscale segmentation scenarios were considered: the base case (0%) and $\pm 5\%$ relative to the baseline thresholds derived from Sample B. The base case threshold values are provided in **Tables S1** and **S2** for 0 min and 33 min, respectively. Mineral density and molecular weight data are listed in **Table S3**. The volume of a voxel is $1.41 \times 10^{-16} m^3$ and the time ($\Delta_{t,0 \text{ to } 33 \text{ min}}$) used to calculate the effective reaction rate after the first 33 minutes is 990 seconds.

Summaries of the parameters used to calculate effective reaction rates for the base case, +5%, and -5% threshold scenarios are presented in **Tables S4**, **S5**, and **S6**, respectively. The overall impact of segmentation on calculated effective reaction rates is summarised in **Table S7**.

Across all minerals and scenarios examined, the sensitivity analysis indicates only negligible variation in dissolution rates relative to the base case, demonstrating that segmentation threshold uncertainty changes the calculated reaction rates by 5% or less.

Table S1. Grayscale threshold values used to define the base-case segmentation for Sample B at 0 min.

Phase	From	To
Outer layer	0	16244
Pore	16244	30460
Microporous phase	30460	34585
Dolomite	34585	38070
Calcite	38070	41130
Anhydrite	41130	64726

Table S2. Grayscale threshold values used to define the base-case segmentation for Sample B at 33 min.

Phase	From	To
Outer layer	0	10314
Pore	10314	30500
Microporous phase	30500	34780
Dolomite	34780	38375
Calcite	38375	41400
Anhydrite	41400	62623

Table S3. Mineral properties used in the effective reaction rate calculation.

Mineral properties	Calcite	Anhydrite	Dolomite	Microporous phase
Density (kg/m^3)	2710	2970	2820	1955
Molecular Weight (kg/mol)	0.1001	0.13614	0.1844	0.1844

Table S4. Summary of parameters used to calculate effective reaction rates for the base case.

Number of voxels	Calcite	Anhydrite	Dolomite	Microporous phase
0 min	$1.38 \times 10^{+8}$	$7.66 \times 10^{+6}$	$2.32 \times 10^{+8}$	$8.57 \times 10^{+7}$
33 min	$1.34 \times 10^{+8}$	$7.58 \times 10^{+6}$	$2.30 \times 10^{+8}$	$8.30 \times 10^{+7}$
Mass (kg)				
0 min	5.25×10^{-5}	3.20×10^{-6}	9.19×10^{-5}	2.35×10^{-5}
33 min	5.10×10^{-5}	3.17×10^{-5}	9.12×10^{-5}	2.28×10^{-5}
Change in mass (kg)				
33 min	1.58×10^{-6}	2.95×10^{-8}	6.92×10^{-7}	7.34×10^{-7}
Number of faces to pore				
0 min	$5.22 \times 10^{+7}$	$4.29 \times 10^{+6}$	$3.84 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.75 \times 10^{+7}$
33 min	$4.85 \times 10^{+7}$	$4.26 \times 10^{+6}$	$3.60 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.67 \times 10^{+7}$
Average number of faces to pore				
0 to 33 min	$5.03 \times 10^{+7}$	$4.27 \times 10^{+6}$	$3.72 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.71 \times 10^{+7}$
Exposed surface area (m²)				
33 min	1.36×10^{-3}	1.16×10^{-4}	1.01×10^{-3}	4.63×10^{-4}
Effective reaction rate (mol/m²s)				
33 min	1.2×10^{-5}	1.9×10^{-6}	3.8×10^{-6}	8.7×10^{-6}

Table S5. Summary of parameters used to calculate effective reaction rates for the 5% more scenario.

Number of voxels	Calcite	Anhydrite	Dolomite	Microporous phase
0 min	$2.77 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.89 \times 10^{+6}$	$2.73 \times 10^{+8}$	$1.45 \times 10^{+8}$
33 min	$2.34 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.78 \times 10^{+6}$	$2.71 \times 10^{+8}$	$1.44 \times 10^{+7}$
Mass (kg)				
0 min	1.06×10^{-5}	7.88×10^{-7}	1.08×10^{-4}	3.99×10^{-5}
33 min	8.93×10^{-6}	7.45×10^{-7}	1.07×10^{-4}	3.95×10^{-5}
Change in mass (kg)				
33 min	1.63×10^{-6}	4.35×10^{-8}	8.76×10^{-7}	4.02×10^{-7}
Number of faces to pore				
0 min	$5.19 \times 10^{+7}$	$6.35 \times 10^{+6}$	$5.02 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.13 \times 10^{+7}$
33 min	$4.83 \times 10^{+7}$	$5.71 \times 10^{+6}$	$4.57 \times 10^{+7}$	$9.27 \times 10^{+6}$
Average number of faces to pore				
0 to 33 min	$5.01 \times 10^{+7}$	$6.03 \times 10^{+6}$	$4.79 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.03 \times 10^{+7}$
Exposed surface area (m²)				
33 min	1.35×10^{-3}	1.63×10^{-4}	1.30×10^{-3}	2.78×10^{-4}
Effective reaction rate (mol/m²s)				
33 min	1.2×10^{-5}	2×10^{-6}	3.7×10^{-6}	7.9×10^{-6}

Table S6. Summary of parameters used to calculate effective reaction rates for the 5% less scenario.

Number of voxels	Calcite	Anhydrite	Dolomite	Microporous phase
0 min	$2.56 \times 10^{+8}$	$7.10 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.19 \times 10^{+8}$	$5.28 \times 10^{+7}$
33 min	$2.29 \times 10^{+8}$	$7.08 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.17 \times 10^{+8}$	$5.15 \times 10^{+7}$
Mass (kg)				
0 min	9.75×10^{-5}	2.97×10^{-5}	4.73×10^{-5}	1.45×10^{-5}
33 min	9.58×10^{-5}	2.96×10^{-5}	4.64×10^{-5}	1.41×10^{-5}
Change in mass (kg)				
33 min	1.75×10^{-6}	7.92×10^{-8}	8.94×10^{-7}	3.78×10^{-7}
Number of faces to pore				
0 min	$5.61 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.21 \times 10^{+7}$	$4.32 \times 10^{+7}$	$9.25 \times 10^{+6}$
33 min	$5.21 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.13 \times 10^{+7}$	$4.96 \times 10^{+7}$	$9.06 \times 10^{+6}$
Average number of faces to pore				
0 to 33 min	$5.41 \times 10^{+7}$	$1.17 \times 10^{+7}$	$4.64 \times 10^{+7}$	$9.16 \times 10^{+6}$
Exposed surface area (m²)				
33 min	1.46×10^{-3}	3.16×10^{-4}	1.25×10^{-3}	2.48×10^{-4}
Effective reaction rate (mol/m²s)				
33 min	1.2×10^{-5}	1.9×10^{-6}	3.9×10^{-6}	8.4×10^{-6}

Table S7. Overview of the impact of segmentation on calculated effective reaction rates.

Effective reaction rate (mol/m ² s) at 33 min	Calcite	Anhydrite	Dolomite	Microporous phase
5% More	1.2×10^{-5}	2×10^{-6}	3.7×10^{-6}	7.9×10^{-6}
Basecase	1.2×10^{-5}	1.9×10^{-6}	3.8×10^{-6}	8.7×10^{-6}
5% Less	1.2×10^{-5}	1.9×10^{-6}	3.9×10^{-6}	8.4×10^{-6}
Difference from basecase (%)				
5% More	0%	-5%	3%	9%
5% Less	0%	0%	-3%	3%

Text S2.

To evaluate the sensitivity of porosity and permeability to segmentation threshold variations, a sensitivity analysis was performed using three grayscale scenarios: 0% (base case) and $\pm 2.5\%$ relative to the baseline thresholds derived from Sample B at 0, 132, and 297 min. An overview of the impact of segmentation on porosity and permeability is provided in **Table S8**. Probability density functions (PDFs) illustrating shifts in velocity distributions across the examined scenarios are presented in **Figure S1**.

The results indicate that the effect of segmentation on porosity and permeability is generally minimal. The most notable differences occur at 0 min, where the +2.5% scenario exhibited a permeability 159% higher than the base case, while the -2.5% scenario showed a permeability 63% lower. Changes in porosity remained small in both cases. At 132 and 297 min, deviations from the base case in both porosity and permeability decreased over time, reflecting a diminishing influence of segmentation threshold on the evolving sample properties, as the overall permeability increased by orders of magnitude.

Table S8. Overview of the impact of segmentation on porosity and permeability.

Scenario	Porosity (<i>fraction</i>)	Permeability (m^2)
2.5% More at 0 min	0.08	1.9×10^{-13}
Basecase at 0 min	0.07	7.7×10^{-14}
2.5% Less at 0 min	0.05	2.9×10^{-14}
2.5% More at 132 min	0.16	2.5×10^{-11}
Basecase at 132 min	0.14	2.1×10^{-11}
2.5% Less at 132 min	0.12	1.9×10^{-11}
2.5% More at 297 min	0.20	4.9×10^{-11}
Basecase at 297 min	0.18	4.7×10^{-11}
2.5% Less at 297 min	0.16	4.4×10^{-11}

Figure S1. Probability density functions (PDFs) illustrating shifts in velocity distributions from the basecase. The dashed line depicts $u/q = 1$.